

THE ROLE OF BIOETHICS IN TEACHING CLINICAL SCIENCES AT MEDICAL
UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: The implementation of bioethical issues in the educational process at medical higher education institutions is considered a crucial priority task in the professional training of future healthcare workers. The solution to this challenge is linked to the introduction of a comprehensive set of bioethics-oriented courses. These courses should have a value-guiding influence, be structured around bioethical problems, and aim to shape students' bioethical thinking and behavior.

Keywords: bioethics, clinical sciences, medical universities.

Currently, the advancement of medical science and practice, as well as the importance of problem-based medical education in societal qualitative changes, is focused on finding appropriate models for bioethical education and training. Simultaneously, addressing the issue of developing socio-professional responsibility is associated with seeking new humanitarian and ethical standards for medical activities and clarifying the content of bioethical concepts.

It is considered appropriate that the model for developing bioethical responsibility in medical university students' personalities be represented by a set of two subsystems encompassing the studied process - continuous educational and didactic systems. During the conducted research, it should outline the prospects for a more in-depth study of the problem of forming bioethical responsibility in the professional activities of medical university students, taking into account additional education, elective courses, and other factors.

Documents adopted by the world healthcare system have already led to the formation of medical legislation, which, in turn, determines the growing demand for a new direction of legal science - medical law, which is a branch of bioethics aimed at protecting human rights in science and medicine. Often, inconsistency of departmental regulatory legal acts with federal regulatory legal acts is observed, which leads to certain legal contradictions, and as a result, objections and even accusations against practicing physicians remain unfounded.

Therefore, let us discuss the aspects that make it appropriate for bioethics to be taught to senior students by clinical departments. For example, in the Department of Propedeutics of Internal Diseases, the focus should be on the fundamental discipline of training specialists in internal medicine, addressing problems of medical ethics related to internal diseases, ethical and legal issues in doctor-patient relationships, and matters of patient consent for medical interventions. In the Department of General Surgery, emphasis should be placed on issues of patient consent for surgical examinations and treatments, as well as the ethical and legal aspects of obtaining consent for surgery. The Department of Pathological Anatomy should cover the bioethical aspects of autopsy and the medical aspects of morphological examination of cadaver samples. The Department of Faculty Therapy should address the development of the euthanasia issue at the end of the 20th and beginning of the 21st centuries, including the medical assessment of active euthanasia based on legislation in several Western European countries and the USA. The Department of Therapy should focus on biomedical problems related to modern achievements in genetics and molecular biology, such as legal

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considerations, attitudes of scientists and various religious representatives towards cloning, and the ethical aspects of obtaining and using stem cells in disease treatment. In the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, important topics include the ethical issues of abortion, rights of pregnant women, distinguishing between the rights of mothers and embryos, regulations on individual rights, and matters of reproductive technology. The Department of Anesthesiology and Reanimatology should cover ethical issues in biomedical practice for anesthesiologists and resuscitation specialists, decision-making regarding disconnecting artificial ventilation, and determining clinical death, biological death, and brain death. The Oncology Department should address palliative care for cancer patients, hospices, training doctors and nurses for proper palliative care, the status of these issues in Western and Eastern European countries, and the ethical aspects of passive euthanasia practices for cancer patients in various countries. The Department of Infectious Diseases should focus on HIV infection and AIDS, biomedical issues in patient examination, problems of collecting and storing information about the disease in various institutions fighting AIDS, and bioethical problems of adequately treating patients with HIV infection. The Department of Forensic Medicine should cover forensic medicine and medical law, bioethical and legal aspects of legal medicine, and ethical issues in forensic examination, forensic criminalistics, forensic chemistry, forensic histology, and forensic biology. The Department of Pediatrics should address children's rights, bioethical problems of children with mental disabilities, and issues of providing care to sick children. Finally, the Department of Psychiatry should focus on the specific features of providing assistance for mental illnesses, the rights of mentally ill patients, and modern legislation and ethical issues related to providing medical care to psychiatric patients.

Thus, each department can independently decide how to address these issues within the context of its subject matter. If these topics are covered comprehensively in lectures and discussed in a series of practical classes, it may be possible to prevent bioethical problems from arising. However, this plan is not strictly mandatory but rather suggestive. Each department can expand or narrow the range of issues based on its own considerations and new developments, or substitute them as needed. Based on the above, we would like to emphasize once again that in clinical departments, professors and teachers not only engage in educational activities but also perform medical duties. This allows them to objectively understand the current problems and needs of healthcare, which in turn enables them to study, analyze, and address these problems and needs from a bioethical perspective.

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